

EFFECT OF GEOGRID REINFORCEMENT ON LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY OF A COARSE SAND BED

Abhishek Singh

TATA Consulting Engineers Limited, India

B. R. Phanikumar

Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore, India

Ram Prasad

Research scholar, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore, India

ABSTRACT

A series of laboratory model tests was conducted to study the improvement in bearing capacity of coarse sands compacted to a relative density of 50%. A surface footing plate of diameter 60 mm was used as the shallow foundation. Circular geogrids of diameter 120 mm were used as horizontal reinforcement layers. The number of geogrids and the spacing between them were varied in the study. It was found that the bearing capacity of loose sand layers improved with introduction of horizontal geogrid reinforcement layer. Bearing capacity was found to improve further with increase in number of geogrid layers and with decrease in spacing between them. The depth to the geogrid layer from the base of the foundation was also varied in the study.

Key words: Bearing Capacity, Geogrid Reinforcement, Relative Density, Shallow Foundation

Cite this Article: Abhishek Singh, B. R. Phanikumar and Ram Prasad. Effect of Geogrid Reinforcement on Load Carrying Capacity of A Coarse Sand Bed, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 7(3), 2016, pp. 01–06.

<http://www.iaeme.com/IJCIET/issues.asp?JType=IJCIET&VType=7&IType=3>

1. INTRODUCTION

Ground improvement has been one of the areas in geotechnical engineering that has been extensively researched into. Various types of ground improvement have been devised depending upon the ground conditions for various types of structures. Heavy tamping, granular piles, thermal treatment, stabiliation with various kinds of chemicals and reinforced earth are some of the ground improvement techniques.

Geosynthetic reinforcement of ground has been a recent development in reinforced earth. Geotextiles, geofabrics and geogrids have been the reinforcement components used for improving bearing capacity of poor soils.

Binquet and Lee (1975) gave a theoretical analysis to find out the pressure intensity of isolated strip footings resting on reinforced earth slab for a given settlement. Ramaswamy and Yong (1983) conducted model tests on strip footings on sand fill, with and without reinforcements. Bearing capacity improved and bearing capacity ratio was found to be in good agreement with the analytical procedures of Binquet and Lee (1976).

Guido et al (1985, 1986) conducted model plate load tests on uniformly graded sand and un-reinforced sand reinforced with layers of different type of geotextiles. The results showed that bearing capacity depended upon u/b ratio (ratio of depth below the footing of the first layer of reinforcement to the width of the footing), s/b (ratio of vertical spacing of the layers of reinforcement to the width of the footing) and number of reinforcement layers. Tests on strip footing resting on loose sand overlying weak clay with geotextile placed at sand-clay interface resulted in increasing bearing capacity with reduction in distance of footing from geotextile layer and increase in the embedment depth (Kim and Cho, 1988) as well as the settlement of footing.

Based on the laboratory experiments conducted by Michalowski et al. (2005) two modes of foundation collapse were suggested, one associated with reinforcement slip and the other associated with tensile failure of reinforcement. Shivashankar et al (1993) studied the improvement in bearing capacity of footings resting on granular bed overlying soft clay assuming a punching shear failure mechanism in the foundation soil. The tensile strains developed in the geogrid provide the confining effect. Madhav and Ramu (1999) developed a new model to represent the granular bed over the soft clay deposit. Many model laboratory and field tests were carried out in the past to simulate the behaviour of reinforced soils. They provide a good understanding of reinforced soil behaviour. This paper presents some experimental data on the effect of geogrid reinforcement on load capacity of a coarse sand bed. Laboratory scale load tests were conducted to study the performance of reinforced foundation sand bed reinforced with geogrids as planar reinforcement. The behaviour and performance of the sand bed reinforced with varying number of geogrid layers at various depths from the base of the footing was studied.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Dry coarse sand was used for preparing the test sand beds. The test sand beds were compacted to a thickness of 200 mm in a cylindrical test tank of diameter 300 mm and a height of 250 mm (see Fig 1). The relative density of all the sand beds was kept constant at 50%. The sand beds were compacted to a dry unit weight (γ_d) corresponding to the predetermined relative density of 50%. Dry unit weight (γ_d) corresponding to $D_r = 50\%$ was determined through pilot tests conducted on all the types of sand by determining the void ratios in their loosest and densest states, namely, e_{max} and e_{min} . By prefixing the relative density at 50%, the void ratio corresponding to this relative density was determined. The sand bed was compacted in four layers, each of thickness 50 mm. The weight of dry sand corresponding to the dry unit weight was measured and divided in to four equal parts. Each part was compacted in the test tank to a thickness of 50 mm. In the case of geogrid reinforcement sand beds, the geogrid layers were placed at the required height, u and

spacing, s . The thickness of all the sand layers was checked in order to ensure the prefixed dry unit weight.

Figure 1

A foundation plate or test plate of diameter 60 mm was used for the conduct of the plate load tests. The diameter of the horizontal geogrid reinforcement was kept equal to 120 mm in all the tests. The number of geogrids was varied as $n = 1, 2$ and 3 . The spacing between the geogrid was kept constant as 10 mm. In the case of tests with $n = 1$ and $n = 2$, the depth to the top geogrid (u) from the base of the foundation (or test plate) was varied as 10 mm and 20 mm. Netlon CE 121 was used for providing horizontal geogrid reinforcement in the sand base. It is a high tensile polypropylene sheet with an aperture size of 6 mm. It has a tensile strength of 7.68 kN/m^2 . When the compaction was over, the test plate was kept on the sand bed at the center of the tank and subjected to loading. Two dial gauges of 0.01 mm sensitivity were fixed to the test plate for observing the deformation under the applied loads. Initially, a seating load of 10 N was applied on the test plate. The subsequent load increments were 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 40 N and 40 N for unreinforced sand beds and 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 30 N and $4 \times 40 \text{ N}$ for geogrid reinforced sand beds chosen arbitrarily. Each load increment was kept on the sand bed for 60 minutes and the deformations observed. The average of deformation readings observed from the two dial gauges was reported as the actual deformation.

3. DISCUSSION

Fig 2 shows the load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand bed and coarse sand bed reinforced with single geogrid ($n=1$) placed at $u = 10 \text{ mm}$ and $u = 20 \text{ mm}$. Horizontal geogrid reinforcement placed beneath the footing intercepts the failure zones in sand beds and helps in increasing the bearing capacity of the foundation system. Further, the stress distribution area increases at a given depth in the sand bed because of a wider dispersion of stress affected by horizontal geogrid reinforcement. Hence, the stress at a given horizontal plane in the sand bed reduces, resulting in a smaller amount of settlement. This leads to higher stiffness of the geogrid reinforced sand layer. For example, the vertical compressive loads required to be applied for deformation of 0.5 mm for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand were respectively

83 N, 44 N and 87 N. When u was increased to 20 mm, the compressive loads required to be applied for the same deformation decreased, indicating that the geogrid would be more effective when placed in a closer proximity to the base of the foundation. The stiffness of the geogrid reinforced sand layer would be higher at lower values of u .

Fig 2. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand bed and coarse sand bed reinforced with single geogrid ($n=1$)

Fig 3 shows load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand and coarse sand reinforced with various configurations of geogrids ($n = 2; s = 10$ and $n = 2; s = 20$) for $u = 10$ mm. The load-settlement curves for $n = 1$ and $u = 10$ mm are also shown for comparison with those for $n = 2$. The load-settlement curves for $n = 2$ were above those for $n = 1$, indicating the improvement in load carrying capacity compared to $n = 1$. With increasing number of geogrids, the interlocking effect and interface friction increase significantly rendering the systems more shear resistant. The higher confinement of sand, which was a consequence of higher number of geogrids, reduced the amount of settlement, thus preventing failure.

Fig 3. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand bed and coarse sand bed reinforced with varying number of geogrids ($n=1, n=2$)

When the spacing between the geogrids (s) was less, the compressive load response was further improved. Fig. 4 shows the load-settlement curves for unreinforced coarse sand beds and coarse sand beds reinforced with $n = 1, n = 2$ and $n = 3$. The data pertain to $u = 10$ mm and $s = 10$ mm. The load-settlement curve for $n = 3$ was lying above all other curves indicating highest improvement in load carrying capacity. The curves for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, in that order, lay below that for $n = 3$.

Fig 4. Load-settlement behaviour for coarse sand bed (n=1, n=2, n=3)

4. CONCLUSION

The geogrid reinforced sand beds resulted in improved load – settlement behavior indicating higher bearing capacity due to geogrid reinforcement. The geogrid-reinforced sand layer was more effective when placed in a closer proximity to the base of the foundation. The load response was better for $u = 10$ mm than $u = 20$ mm. When the spacing between the geogrids (s) was less, the compressive load response was further improved. The load-settlement curve for $n = 3$ was lying above all other curves indicating highest improvement in load carrying capacity. The curves for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, in that order, lay below that for $n = 3$. The load required for $\delta = 0.5$ mm increased with increasing number of geogrids.

REFERENCES

- [1] Binquet, J. and Lee, K.L., (1975a), Bearing capacity analysis of reinforced earth mass, *Journal of geotechnical engineering division, ASCE*, 101(GT12), pp.1241-1255
- [2] Binquet, J. and Lee, K.L., (1975b), Bearing capacity test on reinforced earth slabs, *Journal of technical engineering division, ASCE*, .101(GT12) pp.1257-1276
- [3] Guido, V.A., Biesiadecki, 0.1. and Sullivan, M.J., (1985), Bearing capacity of geotextile reinforced foundation, *Proceedings of 11th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, 3, pp. 1777-1780.
- [4] Guido, V.A., Chang, D.K. and Sweeney, M.A., (1986), Comparison of geogrid and geotextile reinforced earth slabs, *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 23, pp. 435-440.
- [5] Kim, S.I. and Cho, S.D., (1988), An experimental study on the ‘tribution of géotextiles to bearing capacity on footings on week clays, *Proceedings of the International Geotechnical Symposium on Theory and Practice of Earth Reinforcement*, pp. 215-220.
- [6] Michalowski, R.L. and Viratjandr, C., (2005), Two-layer reinforced foundation soils loaded to failure, *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering, ASCE*, 130, pp. 38 1-390.
- [7] Ramaswamy, S.D. and Yong, K.Y., (1983), Cyclic load tests on the reinforced foundation sand beds, *Proceedings 8th European Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, pp. 527-530.

- [8] Ramu, K., Madhav, M.R. and Poorooshasb, H.B., (1999), Finite strain theory for response of granular bed overlying soft ground, *4thAsia-Pacific Conf. on Computational Mechanics*, Singapore.
- [9] K.V. Maheshwari, Dr. A.K. Desai and Dr. C.H. Solanki. Bearing Capacity of Fiber Reinforced Soil, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 4(1), 2013, pp. 159–164.
- [10] Sidramappa Shivashankar Dharane. RCC Beam with Spiral Reinforcement, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 5(8), 2013, pp. 98–100.
- [11] Sanad A.M. and Hassan H.A. Effect of Corrosion on Concrete Reinforcement Mechanical and Physical Properties, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 2013, pp. 176–184.
- [12] Shivashankar, R., Madhav, M.R. and Miura, N., (1993), Reinforced granular beds overlying soft clay, *Proceedings of 11th South-East Asian Geotechnical Conference*, pp. 409-4 14.